

IMPROVING MECHANISMS FOR DEVELOPING THE PROFESSIONAL PEDAGOGICAL SKILLS OF TEACHERS

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Abstract. *In the article, the digitization of all aspects of our life today, including the role of digital technologies in higher education, improving the pedagogical skills of future teachers, the role of digital technologies in training competitive personnel, and the problems of modern education were analyzed. The positive and negative aspects of the introduction of digital technologies in the higher education system, the importance of digital technologies in the development of the professional training of students, and the requirements for their rational and effective use are presented.*

Keywords: *digital education, pedagogical skill, task, efficiency, education, personnel, information and communication technologies, digital technology, cognitive activity, digitization.*

Introduction. In order to solve information problems, it is necessary to form the needs and possibilities of using information and communication technologies from childhood. In this regard, the professional competence of a modern teacher is impossible without special knowledge and skills in collecting, searching, storing, producing, processing, transmitting and using information based on modern microprocessors and computers. Thus, digital technologies should be an integral part of the competence of teachers to assess the quality of education.

Fundamental reform of the education system, training of highly qualified personnel who meet high moral and ethical requirements for the development of the society is the common task of the employees of education system. Theoretical-methodological arming of the educational system aimed at all-round development of the personality is defined as the main goal of pedagogy today. Successful completion of the high, but honorable tasks described above requires high professional skills, knowledge and a broad worldview from each pedagogical employee.

The President of our country Sh.M. Mirziyoyev said, "It is very important to solve another problem: it is the professional level of pedagogues and professors, their special knowledge. In this regard, it is necessary to create an environment that actively supports the processes of education, issues of spiritual and educational maturity, and the formation of real values", and their opinions are very important.

Digital learning is an educational practice that supports the learning process and leads to tangible results. It serves not only to continue the educational process through digital educational tools, but also to increase the quality and efficiency of education. The introduction of digital education into the educational process is carried out on the basis of the use of information technologies. Accordingly, in the modern information society, a pedagogue has a wide range of professional, cognitive skills using computer and communication technologies, including radio, television, modern mobile devices, gadgets, interactive equipment, podcasting, streaming and augmented reality technologies, web services, mobile applications, etc., leisure, the ability to solve household and other tasks has a special place. [4, 70 b]

Analysis of literature on the topic. In order to be a master of pedagogical skills, a teacher should know his subject based on the requirements of the time, have pedagogical and

psychological knowledge, and also possess humanity, curiosity and self-sacrifice. I.P. Rachenko describes pedagogical skill as a part of pedagogical art and writes: "pedagogical skill is the teacher's perfect mastery of pedagogical-psychological knowledge, professional skills and abilities, developed pedagogical thinking and intuition, interest in his profession, it is understood as a moral-aesthetic attitude to life, confidence in one's opinion and strong will".

In the psychological theory of educational activity (P.Ya. Galperin, V.V. Davidov, A.N. Leontev, A.K. Markova, S.L. Rubinshtein, N.F. Talizina, D.B. Elkonin, etc.), the mastery of the teaching content and the development of the student depend on this. It is always qualified that it does not happen through data transmission, but only during its active activity and shows that there is an action with certain characteristics behind the skills. This situation forms the psychological basis of the approach based on learning activities, which has had a great impact on the development of the goals, content and methods of education during the second half of the 20th century.

According to V.I. Zagvyazinskiy, education is an activity-based approach, which implies that "all pedagogical activities are directed to the organization of intensive, increasingly complex activities", because a person can learn science and culture, the world only through his activities and learns the methods of change, forms and improves personal qualities [7, 51 b].

Research methodology. Today, digital technologies are rapidly developing and require keeping up with the times in every field. The use of digital technologies in the education system is of great importance in improving the quality of education and educating socially active young people in the present era, when the speed of information acquisition and use is very high.

We will answer the question of what is digital technology as follows: it is a modern form of business management. In it, a large set of data in digital form and the process of their processing serve as the main factor of production and management. Using the obtained results in practice makes it possible to achieve much greater efficiency compared to traditional forms of management.

Analysis and results. A teacher with high pedagogical skills should be able to understand the child, have a humane attitude towards him, correctly assess any pedagogical situation, eliminate potential conflicts in a timely manner, in pedagogical activities he should always be able to connect the noble idea of progress, social development and the pedagogical process with life.

Digitization of the educational environment can be implemented in various forms: - translation of existing educational materials, including lectures, presentations, textbooks, tasks for independent work and knowledge management tools into an electronic environment for teacher and child-student creation of an interactive electronic environment for interactions between teachers, including the creation of e-classes for teachers, conducting webinars, discussion forums, etc.; creation of new types of educational tools: electronic textbooks, electronic problem books, video lectures, electronic assignment base, computer games; creating radically new forms of education using the possibilities of the electronic environment; expanding the spectrum of imaginary transmission of information, modeling various situations during role-playing games, simulating competitive games, etc.; applying the capabilities of artificial intelligence to the educational process. [p. 6,101]

Pedagogical skills system consists of the following interrelated main components: 1. Pedagogical obedience to humanitarian requirements. 2. Perfect knowledge of professional knowledge in connection with other disciplines. 3. Having pedagogical skills. 4. Thorough mastery of the secrets of pedagogical techniques. [2, p. 75]

Today, it trains young people ideologically and politically, teaches them the laws of nature, society, social life, development of thinking, prepares young people for work, helps them master the secrets of professions, and the socio-economic situation that is important for society. This responsibility requires the teacher to be a master of his profession, to have an educational impact on the students, to develop their interests, abilities, talents, beliefs and practical skills in every way. It requires a professional to find them.

Conclusions and suggestions. In short, if education is provided through digital technologies, the methods of education become easier for students. Training teachers with such tools ensures the improvement of the quality of education. We all know that the use of digital technologies in online classes has a good effect. For example, we can consider online classes given on television as a type of digital education. In this context, lessons on "pedagogical skills" for future teachers are digital technologies as a means of increasing efficiency.

Tasks are as follows:

- to ensure the enrichment of the educational content based on the prospects of social and economic development of the country, the needs of society, modern achievements of science, culture, technique and technology; - to develop and introduce quick methods of effective use of our national customs and traditions, our rich literary heritage in the development of the spiritual and moral outlook of future teachers; - to enrich the education and training process with normative documents, teaching-methodical literature, material-technical and information base in order to ensure the quality and the guarantees of its stable development to the level required from teachers in the future.

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